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Pentatomoidea (Hemiptera: Heteroptera) of Greece – An annotated checklist

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Abstract: An annotated checklist of 148 species of the Greek Pentatomoidea (Hemiptera: Heteroptera) is provided, which updates the previous checklist of DROSOPOULOS (1980). Comments are provided for doubtful species and taxonomic updates, rare species and species new to Greece since 1980. Twenty-three species are recorded new to Greece since 1980.

Key words: Hemiptera, Heteroptera, Pentatomoidea, Acanthosomatidae, Cydnidae, Pentatomidae, Plataspidae, Scutelleridae, Thyreocoridae, checklist, Greece.

Introduction

REUTER (1891) recorded 58 species in five families of Pentatomoidea from a number of sites throughout Greece. DROSOPOULOS (1980) provided an updated catalogue of known species of Heteroptera as part of his review of the Greek Hemiptera, which included 125 species and subspecies of Pentatomoidea in six families. Within the current paper 23 additional species are recorded from Greece, and the taxonomic status of a number of species has been revised. A summary of the changes in the known Pentatomoidea fauna from Greece is shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Number of recorded species of Pentatomoidea in Greece from REUTER to present day.

	Acantho- somati- dae	Cydnidae	Pentato- midae	Plataspi- dae	Scutel- leridae	Thyreocor- idae	Total
REUTER, 1891	2	8	39	0	8	1	58
DROSO- POULOS, 1980	5	20	78	1	20	1	125
This paper	4	29	92	1	21	1	148

Material and Methods

The checklist updates the previous catalogue of DROSOPOULOS (1980) and updates and expands that work for the Pentatomoidea to include all new species recorded in Greece since 1980. Nomenclature follows the Palearctic catalogue (AUKEMA & RIEGER 2006) updated by the supplemental catalogue (AUKEMA *et al.* 2013) and updated taxonomic reviews (BELOUSOVA 2007, DERJANSCHI & PÉRICART 2005, DURSUN & FENT 2013, GAPON 2007, 2018, LUPOLI 2017, LUPOLI *et al.* 2013, RIBES & GAPON 2006, RIBES & PAGOLA-CARTE 2013, PÉRICART 2010). The work of LIS (2014) is acknowledged in providing details of checklist format.

Results

Checklist of species

Synonyms include species only relevant to Greek fauna, for full list of synonyms see AUKEMA & RIEGER (2006) and AUKEMA *et al.* (2013)

*Indicates species not listed in DROSOPOULOS (1980)

Superfamily: Pentatomoidea LEACH, 1815

Family: Cydnidae BILLBERG, 1820

Subfamily: Cydninae BILLBERG, 1820

Tribe: Cydnini BILLBERG, 1820

Cydnus FABRICIUS, 1803

1. ***Cydnus aterrimus*** (FORSTER, 1771)
Cimex tristis FABRICIUS, 1775
Brachypelta atterimus (FORSTER, 1771)

Tribe: Geotomini WAGNER, 1963

Aethus DALLAS, 1851

2. ***Aethus hispidulus*** (KLUG, 1845)
Cydnus hispidulus KLUG, 1845
Cydnus sahlbergi REUTER, 1900

DROSOPOULOS (1980) mis-spelled this species as *A. sahlebergi* (REUTER).

3. ****Aethus pilosus*** (HERRICH-SCHAEFFER, 1834)
Cydnus pilosus HERRICH-SCHAEFFER, 1834

Listed in Greece by LIS (1999; 2006a).

Byrsinus FIEBER, 1860

4. ****Byrsinus balcanicus*** (JOSIFOV, 1986)
Aethus balcanicus JOSIFOV, 1986

Recorded from NE Greece and Crete (JOSIFOV 1986b). Transferred by LIS (1993) to *Byrsinus* FIEBER.

5. ***Byrsinus pilosulus*** (KLUG, 1845)
Cydnus pilosulus KLUG, 1845

Geotomus MULSANT & REY, 1866

6. ***Geotomus brunnipennis*** WAGNER, 1953

7. ***Geotomus ciliatitylus*** SIGNORET, 1881

Note: DROSOPOULOS (1980) cites *G. caucasicus ciliatitylus* (SIGNORET) which is not listed as

a synonym in LIS (2006a). LIS (2006a) cites only *G. ciliatitylus* SIGNORET for Greece which is followed here.

8. ***Geotomus elongatus*** (HERRICH-SCHAEFFER, 1840)

Cydnus caucasicus KOLENATI, 1846

Note: DROSOPOULOS (1980) listed both *G. elongatus* (HERRICH-SCHAEFFER) and *G. caucasicus caucasicus* (KOLENATI) for Greece. *G. caucasicus* (KOLENATI) was synonymised with *G. elongatus* (HERRICH-SCHAEFFER) by KERZHNER (2003).

9. ***Geotomus punctulatus*** (A. COSTA, 1847)

Macroscythus FIEBER, 1860

10. ***Macroscythus brunneus*** (FABRICIUS, 1803)

Microporus UHLER, 1872

11. ****Microporus nigrita*** (FABRICIUS, 1794)

Listed by LIS (1999, 2006a) in Greece without precise locality.

Subfamily: Sehirinae AMYOT & SERVILLE, 1843

Tribe: Amaurocorini Wagner, 1963

Amaurocoris STÅL, 1865

12. ****Amaurocoris curtus*** (BRULLÉ, 1839)

Note: LIS (1999) cited the authority as BRULLÉ, 1838, subsequently listed as BRULLÉ, 1839 in LIS (2006a) but without comment. Recorded from Santorini (RIEGER 1995) and listed from Greece (LIS 1999; LIS 2006a; GHAHARI *et al.* 2009) without precise locality. Recorded from the Greek mainland (de JONG Y. *et al.* 2014). Not listed by LIS & ZIAJA (2015) as occurring in Greece. Recorded from Faliraki, Rhodes in 2017 (BOŠČÍK 2017).

Tribe: Sehirini AMYOT & SERVILLE, 1843

Adomerus MULSANT & REY, 1866

13. ***Adomerus maculipes*** (MULSANT & REY, 1852)

Cydnus maculipes MULSANT & REY, 1852

Canthophorus (Canthophorus) maculipes: MULSANT & REY, 1866

Transferred by GAPON (2018) to *Adomerus* MULSANT & REY.

Canthophorus MULSANT & REY, 1866

14. ***Canthophorus dubius*** (SCOPOLI, 1763)

Cimex dubius SCOPOLI, 1763

Sehirus dubius (SCOPOLI, 1763)

Canthophorus (Canthophorus) dubius MULSANT & REY, 1866

Listed in Greece by LIS (1999, 2006a); not listed by GAPON (2018).

15. ***Canthophorus melanopterus melanopterus*** (HERRICH-SCHAEFFER, 1835)

Cydnus melanopterus HERRICH-SCHAEFFER, 1835

GAPON'S (2018) revision of *Canthophorus* MULSANT & REY adds records of *C. melanopterus melanopterus* (HERRICH-SCHAEFFER) from central Greece (Athens, Evia and Lake Kremasta).

16. ****Crocistethus basalis*** (FIEBER, 1861)

Ochetostethus basalis FIEBER, 1861

Recorded from Santorini by RIEGER (1995) and listed by LIS (1999, 2006a) in Greece.

17. ****Crocistethus waltlianus*** (FIEBER, 1837)

Cydnus waltlianus FIEBER, 1837

Listed for Greece (LIS 1999, 2006a, GHAHARI *et al.* 2009) without precise locality. The author has found this species on Santorini (Perissa, 26.vii.2009, 36°21'33.80"N 25°28'26.55"E).

***Legnotus* SCHIÖDTE, 1848**

18. ***Legnotus fumigatus*** (A. COSTA, 1853)

19. ***Legnotus limbosus*** (GEOFFROY, 1785)

Cimex albomarginatus GOEZE, 1778

Cimex limbosus GEOFFROY in FOURCROY, 1785

Incorrectly listed in Pentatomidae by DROSOPOULOS (1980).

20. ****Legnotus picipes*** (FALLÉN, 1807)

GÜNTHER (1990) cites a record from Nissakis, Kerkyra (Corfu). RIEGER (2007) added a montane record from Falakro Oros, Dramas, NE Greece. Not listed for Greece in LIS (1999, 2006a) but updated to include Greece in AUKEMA *et al.* (2013).

***Ochetostethus* FIEBER, 1860**

21. ***Ochetostethus balcanicus*** WAGNER, 1940

22. ****Ochetostethus heissi*** MAGNIEN, 2006

Not cited from Greece in LIS (1999, 2006a), updated in AUKEMA *et al.* (2013) to include Greece. New to Greece from Natural History Museum, London specimen collected by G.C. Champion from Thessaloniki, NE Greece (MAGNIEN 2006), previously confused with *O. balcanicus* WAGNER or *O. opacus* (SCHOLTZ).

23. ****Ochetostethus opacus*** (SCHOLTZ, 1847)

GÜNTHER (1990) recorded *O. opacus* (SCHOLTZ) from sites in northern Greece and it was recorded from Santorini by RIEGER (1995). Listed in LIS (1999, 2006a) for Greece without precise locality, although records prior to MAGNIEN (2006) may include *O. heissi* MAGNIEN.

Note: DROSOPOULOS (1980), GÜNTHER (1990) and WAGNER (1956) list *O. nanus* (HERRICH-SCHAEFFER) for Greece. LIS (2006a) notes that *O. nanus* (HERRICH-SCHAEFFER, 1834) occurs only in the southwest Mediterranean and that records for other areas probably refer to *O. opacus* (SCHOLTZ) and it is not listed for Greece by LIS (1999, 2006a) or by AUKEMA *et al.* (2013).

***Shirus* AMYOT & SERVILLE, 1843**

24. ****Shirus luctuosus*** MULSANT & REY, 1866

Listed by LIS (1999, 2006a) for Greece without precise locality.

25. ***Shirus morio*** (LINNAEUS, 1761)

Cydnus affinis HERRICH-SCHAEFFER, 1830

26. ***Shirus ovatus*** (HERRICH-SCHAEFFER, 1840)

***Singeria* WAGNER, 1955**

27. ***Singeria brevipennis*** WAGNER, 1955

DROSOPOULOS (1980) incorrectly placed this species in the genus *Shirus*. STICHEL (1960-62) erroneously listed *S. brevipennis* WAGNER from Corfu, however the original specimens in the Zoological Museum of Hamburg (2 exx., holotype and paratype) were collected by Paganetti-Hummler on Cephalonia and were cited as such by WAGNER (1955). Endemic to Greece.

***Tritomegas* AMYOT & SERVILLE, 1843**

28. ****Tritomegas bicolor*** (LINNAEUS, 1758)

Cimex bicolor LINNAEUS, 1758

Tritomegas bicolor AMYOT & SERVILLE, 1843

Listed in LIS (1999, 2006a) for Greece without precise locality.

29. ***Tritomegas sexmaculatus*** (RAMBUR, 1839)

Cydnius sexmaculatus RAMBUR, 1839

Canthophorus (Tritomegas) sexmaculatus MULSANT & REY, 1866

Tritomegas sexmaculatus GARBIGLIETTI, 1869

Family: Thyreocoridae AMYOT & SERVILLE, 1843

Included by DROSPOULOS (1980) in Cydnidae, now raised to family rank (LIS 2006b).

Subfamily: Thyreocorinae AMYOT & SERVILLE, 1843

Thyreocoris SCHRANK, 1801.

30. ***Thyreocoris scarabaeoides*** (LINNAEUS, 1758)

Family: Plataspidae DALLAS, 1851

Subfamily: Coptosomatinae KIRKALDY, 1909

Coptosoma LAPORTE, 1833

31. ***Coptosoma scutellatum*** (GEOFFROY, 1785)

Cimex scutellatus GEOFFROY IN FOURCROY, 1785

Cimex globus FABRICIUS, 1794

Coptosoma scutellatum scutellatum (GEOFFROY, 1785)

Listed by DAVIDOVÁ-VILÍMOVÁ (2006) for Greece but without precise locality.

Family: Acanthosomatidae SIGNORET, 1864

Subfamily: Acanthosomatinae SIGNORET, 1864

Acanthosoma CURTIS, 1824

32. ***Acanthosoma haemorrhoidale haemorrhoidale*** (LINNAEUS, 1758)

A rare species in Greece with an old record from Corfu (GULDE 1928).

Cyphostethus FIEBER, 1860

33. ***Cyphostethus tristriatus*** (FABRICIUS, 1787)

Elasmostethus FIEBER, 1860

34. ***Elasmostethus interstinctus*** (LINNAEUS, 1758)

Elasmucha STÅL, 1864

35. ***Elasmucha grisea grisea*** (LINNAEUS, 1758)

Clinocoris antennatus REUTER, 1885

Family: Scutelleridae LEACH, 1815

All species were incorrectly listed in the Pentatomidae by DROSPOULOS (1980).

Subfamily: Elvisurinae STÅL, 1872

Solenosthedium SPINOLA, 1837

36. ***Solenosthedium bilunatum*** (LEFEBVRE, 1827)

A scarce species in the eastern Mediterranean, with recent records from Cyprus (RAMSAY 2016), southern Turkey (YILDIRIM *et al.* 2014) and Croatia (GOGALA 2008). Recent Greek records are from Agis Apostoli, Crete, 28.v.2003; Neochori, Preveza, NW Greece, 11 - 20.v. 2000 (NMPC, PETR KMENT, pers. comm.) and Iliia, NW Peloponnese (LEONIDAS-ROMANOS DAVRANOGLU, pers. comm.).

Subfamily: Odontotarsinae MULSANT & REY, 1865

Tribe Odontotarsini MULSANT & REY, 1866

37. *Odontotarsus caudatus* (BURMEISTER, 1835)

Pachycoris caudatus BURMEISTER, 1835

38. **Odontotarsus crassus* KIRITSCHENKO, 1966

Odontotarsus latissimus GÖLLNER-SCHIEDING, 1990

Note. GÖLLNER-SCHIEDING (1990) described *O. latissimus* GÖLLNER-SCHIEDING, 1990 as a new species with a distribution including Crete, subsequently listed for Greece by GÖLLNER-SCHIEDING (2006). CARAPEZZA (2009) synonymised *O. latissimus* GÖLLNER-SCHIEDING with *O. crassus* KIRITSCHENKO. Listed for Greece by AUKEMA *et al.* (2013) under *O. crassus* KIRITSCHENKO.

39. *Odontotarsus freyi* PUTON, 1882

40. *Odontotarsus parvulus* HORVÁTH, 1917

41. **Odontotarsus plicatulus* HORVÁTH, 1906

Odontotarsus confraginosus HOBERLANDT, 1956

Not listed by GÖLLNER-SCHIEDING (1990) for Greece, subsequently listed from Greece (GÖLLNER-SCHIEDING 2006) without specific locality.

42. *Odontotarsus purpureolineatus* (ROSSI, 1790)

Odontotarsus purpureolineatus f. *confluens* HOBERLANDT, 1944

43. *Odontotarsus robustus* JAKOVLEV, 1884

44. *Odontotarsus rufescens* FIEBER, 1861

Odontotarsus rufescens var. *irroratus* HORVÁTH, 1881

Odontotarsus irroratus HORVÁTH, 1882

Odontotarsus rufescens var. *vittiger* HORVÁTH, 1906

Note. HOBERLANDT (1956) listed *O. rufescens* var. *irroratus* HORVÁTH from Greece, but incorrectly cited 1881 as the year of publication.

Subfamily: Odontoscelinae AMYOT & SERVILLE, 1843

Irochrotus AMYOT & SERVILLE, 1843

45. *Irochrotus maculiventris* (GERMAR, 1839)

Arctocoris villosus HERRICH-SCHAEFFER, 1839

JOSIFOV (1959) recorded *Irochrotus maculiventris* (GERMAR) from Thasos. GÖLLNER-SCHIEDING (2006) considers that eastern records of *I. lanatus* (PALLAS, 1773); (including Greece) are confused with *I. maculiventris* (GERMAR) and there are no confirmed records of *I. lanatus* (PALLAS) in Greece.

Odontoscelis LAPORTE, 1833

46. **Odontoscelis byrrhus* SEIDENSTÜCKER, 1972

Recorded from Greece; Zante, Crete, Rhodes and the Cyclades (GÖLLNER-SCHIEDING 1986) and Santorini (RIEGER 1995). Listed for Greece by GÖLLNER-SCHIEDING (2006).

47. *Odontoscelis fuliginosa* (LINNAEUS, 1761)

48. *Odontoscelis lineola* RAMBUR, 1839

Odontoscelis dubia WAGNER, 1957

Note: DROSPOULOS (1980) listed *O. dubius* (= *dubia*) (WAGNER), which was synonymised with *O. lineola* RAMBUR by KERZHNER (1976) (GÖLLNER-SCHIEDING 1986, 2006).

49. **Odontoscelis minuta* JAKOVLEV, 1882

Recorded from Crete (GÖLLNER-SCHIEDING 1986) and listed for Greece without precise locality (GÖLLNER-SCHIEDING 2006).

Note: DROSPOULOS (1980) lists *Odontoscelis dorsalis* (FABRICIUS), which is not listed for Greece by GÖLLNER-SCHIEDING (1986, 2006). GÖLLNER-SCHIEDING (1986) keys all species of *Odontoscelis* and *O. dorsalis* (FABRICIUS) and *O. lineola* RAMBUR are separated at the same couplet on geographical distribution; in addition, two subspecies of *O. dorsalis* f. *deserta* STICHEL, 1924 and *O. dorsalis* var. *carbonaria* KORMILEV, 1939 are considered by GÖLLNER-SCHIEDING (2006) as synonyms of *O. lineola* RAMBUR. The true *O. dorsalis* (FABRICIUS, 1798) is considered absent from Greece without confirmed examples.

Subfamily: Eurygastrinae AMYOT & SERVILLE, 1843

Eurygaster LAPORTE, 1833

Note: Numerous varieties were described by early authors due to the variability of species; only those pertaining to Greece are cited here.

50. ***Eurygaster austriaca*** (SCHRANK, 1776)
Eurygaster austriaca austriaca (SCHRANK, 1776)
51. ***Eurygaster dilaticollis*** DOHRN, 1860
Eurygaster brevicollis FIEBER, 1861
52. ***Eurygaster integriceps*** PUTON, 1881
Eurygaster integriceps var. *nigra* REUTER, 1900
Eurygaster integriceps var. *ferruginea* REUTER, 1900
Eurygaster integriceps var. *testacea* REUTER, 1900
Eurygaster integriceps var. *hellenica* KIRKALDY, 1909
Eurygaster maurus var. *nigricans* KIRKALDY, 1909
53. ***Eurygaster maura*** (LINNAEUS, 1758)
54. ***Eurygaster testudinaria testudinaria*** (GEOFFROY, 1785)
Eurygaster maura var. *grisescens* REY, 1888

Note: DROSPOULOS (1980) lists *Eurygaster hottentotta* (FABRICIUS, 1775). There are no authenticated Greek examples of *E. hottentotta*. RIEGER (1995) cited an old record of 'E. hottentottus' from Santorini which he assigned to *E. austriaca* (SCHRANK). In the Palearctic, *E. hottentotta* has been variously ascribed to *E. austriaca* (SCHRANK), *E. integriceps* PUTON and *E. maura* (L.) (GÖLLNER-SCHIEDING 2006).

Psacasta GERMAR, 1839

55. ***Psacasta exanthematica exanthematica*** (SCOPOLI, 1763)
- Note: CARAPEZZA & KERZHNER (2005) reviewed the subgenus *Psacasta* and confirmed only the subspecies *P. e. exanthematica* (SCOPOLI) for Greece.
56. ***Psacasta tuberculata*** (FABRICIUS, 1781)

Family: Pentatomidae LEACH, 1815

Subfamily: Asopinae AMYOT & SERVILLE, 1843

Andrallus BERGROTH, 1906

57. ****Andrallus spinidens*** (FABRICIUS, 1787)
- Recorded new to Greece from the Peloponnese by RIEGER (2007).

Arma HAHN, 1832

58. ***Arma insperata*** HORVÁTH, 1899

Jalla HAHN, 1832

59. ***Jalla dumosa*** (LINNAEUS, 1758)

Perillus STÄL, 1862

60. **Perillus bioculatus* (FABRICIUS, 1775)

PÉRICART (2010) and PROTIĆ & ŽIVIĆ (2012) cite records of *P. bioculatus* (FABRICIUS) from Larissa in central Greece. This is one of the few non-montane records for established populations in Europe of this North American predatory species, originally introduced to control the Colorado beetle *Leptinotarsa decemlineata* SAY.

Picromerus AMYOT & SERVILLE, 1843

61. **Picromerus conformis* (HERRICH-SCHAEFFER, 1841)

GÜNTHER (1990) records *P. conformis* (HERRICH-SCHAEFFER) from Nea Malgara, NE Greece. Recorded from Greece by RIDER (2006) without specific locality.

62. *Picromerus nigridentis* (FABRICIUS, 1803)

Pinthaeus STÄL, 1868

63. *Pinthaeus sanguinipes* (FABRICIUS, 1781)

Troilus STÄL, 1868

64. *Troilus luridus* (FABRICIUS, 1775)

Zicrona Amyot & Serville, 1843

65. *Zicrona caerulea* (LINNAEUS, 1758)

Subfamily: Pentatominae LEACH, 1815

Tribe: Aeliini DOUGLAS & SCOTT, 1865

Aelia FABRICIUS, 1803

66. *Aelia acuminata* (LINNAEUS, 1758)

Aelia pallida KÜSTER, 1852

67. **Aelia albovittata* FIEBER, 1868

Recorded without specific locality from Greece by RIDER (2006). CHALDAIOU (2015) cites records from Samos and Chios based on specimens in the Drosopoulos collection.

68. *Aelia furcula* FIEBER, 1868

69. *Aelia klugii* HAHN, 1833

70. *Aelia rostrata* BOHEMAN, 1852

Aelia rostrata var. *glebana* FERRARI, 1874

71. *Aelia virgata* (HERRICH-SCHAEFFER, 1841)

DROSPOULOS (1980) incorrectly cites KLUG as the authority for this species.

Neottiglossa W. KIRBY, 1837

72. *Neottiglossa bifida* (A. COSTA, 1847)

73. *Neottiglossa flavomarginata* (LUCAS, 1849)

74. *Neottiglossa leporina* (HERRICH-SCHAEFFER, 1830)

Tribe: Cappaeini ATKINSON, 1888

75. **Halyomorpha halys* (STÄL, 1855)

Recorded new to Greece from Athens in 2011 (MILONAS & PARTSINEVELOU 2014) and subsequently recorded from Thessaloniki (CIANFERONI *et al.* 2018). A southeast Asian species (RABITSCH 2008) now recorded from several European countries.

Tribe: Carpocorini MULSANT & REY, 1866

Antheminia MULSANT & REY, 1866

Listed under *Codophila* MULSANT & REY by DROSOPOULOS (1980).

76. ***Antheminia lunulata*** (GOEZE, 1778)
Cimex lunulata GOEZE, 1778
Cimex lynx FABRICIUS, 1794
Codophila (Antheminia) lunulata f. *eckerleini* TAMANINI, 1961
77. ***Antheminia varicornis*** (JAKOVLEV, 1874)
Mormidea varicornis JAKOVLEV, 1874
Dolycoris varicornis montandoni SIENKIEWICZ 1954
- DROSOPOULOS (1980) incorrectly cited the authority as JAKOWLEW.

Brachynema MULSANT & REY, 1852

78. ***Brachynema cinctum*** (FABRICIUS, 1775)
79. ***Brachynema germarii*** (KOLENATI, 1846)

Carpocoris KOLENATI, 1846

This genus has undergone considerable revision in recent years. It is perhaps unfortunate that two contrasting treatments of the species group in the West Palearctic appeared almost simultaneously in 2013 (LUPOLI *et al.* 2013, RIBES & PAGOLA-CARTE 2013). The updated Palearctic Catalogue (AUKEMA *et al.* 2013) follows RIBES & PAGOLA-CARTE (2013) in regarding *C. mediterraneus* TAMANINI, as a synonym of *C. fuscispinus* (BOHEMAN), however LUPOLI *et al.* (2013) regard *C. mediterraneus* TAMANINI as a good species and this treatment is followed here. Confirmation of species in Greece is desired.

80. ****Carpocoris fuscispinus*** (BOHEMAN, 1851)
TAMANINI (1959) considered this species absent from Greece, and it was subsequently listed from Greece by RIDER (2006) without specific locality.
81. ***Carpocoris mediterraneus mediterraneus*** TAMANINI, 1958
Listed for Greece by RIDER (2006) and confirmed for Greece by LUPOLI *et al.* (2013) but without precise locality.
82. ***Carpocoris pudicus*** (PODA, 1761)
Listed for Greece by RIDER (2006) without specific locality. WAGNER (1956) lists localities in the Ionian Islands.
83. ****Carpocoris purpureipennis*** (DEGEER, 1773)
Cimex nigricornis FABRICIUS, 1775
Cited from Greece (RIDER 2006, RIBES & PAGOLA-CARTE 2013) but without precise locality.

Chlorochroa STÅL, 1872

84. ***Chlorochroa juniperina juniperina*** (LINNAEUS, 1758)
Pitedia juniperina (LINNAEUS, 1758)
Mis-spelt by DROSOPOULOS (1980) as *P. junipeuna* (L.)
85. ****Chlorochroa pinicola*** (MULSANT & REY, 1852)
Pitedia pinicola (MULSANT & REY, 1852)
Recorded from the Peloponnese (RIBES & PAGOLA-CARTE 2013), not listed for Greece in RIDER (2006) or AUKEMA *et al.* (2013).

Chroantha STÅL, 1872

86. ***Chroantha ornatula*** (HERRICH-SCHAEFFER, 1841)
Codophila MULSANT & REY, 1866

87. *Codophila varia* (FABRICIUS, 1787)
Codophila varia varia (FABRICIUS, 1787)
Dolycoris MULSANT & REY, 1866
88. *Dolycoris baccarum* (LINNAEUS, 1758)
Cimex verbasci DE GEER, 1773
Holcogaster FIEBER, 1860
89. *Holcogaster fibulata* (GERMAR, 1831)
Holcogaster fibulata var. *exilis* HORVÁTH, 1903
Holcogaster longicornis WAGNER, 1955
Holcogaster weberi WAGNER, 1964
- Listed as two species, *H. exilis* (HORVÁTH) and *H. fibulata* (GERMAR) by DROSOPoulos (1980), synonymised by RIBES & GAPON (2006) and listed as *H. fibulata* (GERMAR) in AUKEMA *et al.* (2013). Widespread in Greece (RIBES & PAGOLA-CARTE 2013).
- Holcostethus*** FIEBER, 1860
90. *Holcostethus albipes* (FABRICIUS, 1781)
91. **Holcostethus sphaelatus* (FABRICIUS, 1794)
GÜNTHER (1990) records *H. sphaelatus* (FABRICIUS) new to Greece from the Vourinos mountains, NW Greece. Listed from Greece by RIDER (2006) without precise locality.
- Palomena*** MULSANT & REY, 1866
92. *Palomena prasina* (LINNAEUS, 1761)
Cimex dissimilis FABRICIUS, 1781
Peribalus MULSANT & REY, 1866
93. *Peribalus strictus strictus* (FABRICIUS, 1803)
Holcostethus strictus (FABRICIUS, 1803)
Cimex vernalis WOLFF, 1804
Holcostethus strictus vernalis (WOLFF, 1804)
- BELOUSOVA (2007) confirmed specimens of *P. strictus vernalis* (WOLFF, 1804) from Attica (Athens), which was synonymised with *P. strictus* (FABRICIUS, 1803) by RIBES *et al.* (2006), and is listed as *P. strictus strictus* (FABRICIUS) by AUKEMA *et al.* (2013). Widespread in Greece, including Crete (RIBES & PAGOLA-CARTE 2013).
- Staria*** DOHRN, 1860
94. *Staria lunata* (HAHN, 1835)
- Tribe: Eysarcorini** MULSANT & REY, 1866
- Eysarcoris*** HAHN, 1834
Stollia ELLENRIEDER, 1862
95. *Eysarcoris ventralis* (WESTWOOD, 1837)
Pentatoma inconspicuum HERRICH-SCHAEFFER, 1844
Eysarcoris inconspicuus (HERRICH-SCHAEFFER, 1844)
Eusarcoris helferi FIEBER, 1861
Stagonomus GORSKI, 1852
96. *Stagonomus amoenus* (BRULLÉ, 1832)
97. *Stagonomus bipunctatus* (LINNAEUS, 1758)
Pentatoma pusillum HERRICH-SCHAEFFER, 1833

98. **Stagonomus devius* SEIDENSTÜCKER, 1965
Not listed from Greece by DERJANSCHI & PÉRICART (2005) or RIDER (2006). Recorded from the Peloponnese by RIEGER (2007); listed in Greece by AUKEMA *et al.* (2013).
99. **Stagonomus grenieri* (SIGNORET, 1865)
Recorded from sites in the Peloponnese (DERJANSCHI & PÉRICART 2005). Listed from Greece by RIDER (2006) without specific locality.
100. **Stagonomus venustissimus* (SCHRANK, 1776)
Eysarcoris fabricii KIRKALDY, 1904
Transferred to *Stagonomus* GORSKI by ROCA-CUSACHS & JUNG (2019). Not listed for Greece (RIDER 2006, AUKEMA *et al.* 2013). RIEGER (2012) recorded *S. venustissimus* (SCHRANK) from the Olympus mountains, Leptokarya.

Tribe: Halyini AMYOT & SERVILLE, 1843

Aphodiphus SPINOLA, 1837

101. *Aphodiphus amygdali* (GERMAR, 1817)
Mustha AMYOT & SERVILLE, 1843
102. *Mustha spinosula* (LEFEBVRE, 1831)

Tribe: Mecideini DISTANT, 1902

Mecidea DALLAS, 1851

103. *Mecidea lindbergi* WAGNER, 1954

Tribe: Menidini ATKINSON, 1888

Neostrachia SAUNDERS, 1877

104. *Neostrachia bisignata* (WALKER, 1867)
Rhaphigaster bisignatus WALKER, 1867
Neostrachia hellenica SAUNDERS, 1877
Menida elongata DISTANT, 1902
Apines bisignata (WALKER, 1867)

A rare species in Greece which has been found rarely since first described from Greece by SAUNDERS (1877) and later synonymised with *Rhaphigaster bisignatus* WALKER, with only two modern records (RIEGER 2007, RIBES & PAGOLA-CARTE 2013).

Tribe: Pentatomini LEACH, 1815

Acrosternum FIEBER, 1860

105. **Acrosternum arabicum* WAGNER, 1959
Cited from Greece by RIDER (2006) and by RIBES & PAGOLA-CARTE (2013), but with no additional details.
106. *Acrosternum heegeri* FIEBER, 1861
Nezara heegeri (FIEBER, 1861)
107. **Acrosternum malickyi* JOSIFOV & HEISS, 1989
First recorded as a new species from Crete by JOSIFOV & HEISS (1989) and subsequently recorded in the Peloponnese by RIEGER (2007) and listed for mainland Greece by AUKEMA *et al.* (2013). Endemic to Greece.
108. *Acrosternum millierei* (MULSANT & REY, 1866)

Nezara AMYOT & SERVILLE, 1843

109. *Nezara viridula* (LINNAEUS, 1758)

Cimex torquatus FABRICIUS, 1775

Cimex smaragdulus FABRICIUS, 1775

Note: Both var. *smaragdula* and var. *torquata* occur in Greece.

110. **Pentatoma rufipes* (LINNAEUS, 1758)

Omitted from DROSOPOULOS (1980). Reuter (1891) recorded this species from 'Morea' (Peloponnese) on Apollo fir, a variant of Greek fir *Abies cephalonica* LOUDON. Recorded from the northern mountains of Greece by RIEGER (2007).

Rhaphigaster LAPORTE, 1833

111. *Rhaphigaster nebulosa* (PODA, 1761)

Tribe: Piezodorini ATKINSON, 1888

Piezodorus FIEBER, 1860

112. *Piezodorus lituratus* (FABRICIUS, 1794)

Pentatoma alliaceum GERMAR, 1824

Tribe: Sciocorini AMYOT & SERVILLE, 1843

Dyroderes SPINOLA, 1837

113. *Dyroderes umbraculatus* (FABRICIUS, 1775)

Sciocoris FALLÉN, 1829

114. **Sciocoris convexiusculus* PUTON, 1874

Sciocoris sahlbergi WAGNER 1952

HOBERLANDT (1997) recorded this species from Lesvos, listed by RIDER (2006) for Greece (Lesvos).

115. *Sciocoris cursitans cursitans* (FABRICIUS, 1794)

116. *Sciocoris deltocephalus* FIEBER, 1861

117. *Sciocoris helferii* FIEBER, 1851

118. *Sciocoris macrocephalus* FIEBER, 1851

119. *Sciocoris maculatus* FIEBER, 1851

120. **Sciocoris microphthalmus* FLOR, 1860

DERJANSCHI & PÉRICART (2005) cite records from the Peloponnese. Listed in RIDER (2006) from Greece without precise locality.

121. **Sciocoris ochraceus* FIEBER, 1861

Not listed in DERJANSCHI & PÉRICART (2005). Listed by RIDER (2006) from Greece but without specific locality.

122. **Sciocoris pictus* WAGNER, 1959

DERJANSCHI & PÉRICART (2005) cite a record from Greece but with no precise locality. Listed in RIDER (2006) from Greece.

123. *Sciocoris sulcatus* FIEBER, 1851

Sciocoris atticus (HORVÁTH, 1907)

Tribe: Strachiini MULSANT & REY, 1866

Bagrada STÅL, 1862

124. **Bagrada abeillei* PUTON, 1881
DERJANSCHI & PÉRICART (2005) cite a record from Tripolis in the Peloponnese. Listed for Greece by RIDER (2006) with no specific locality.
125. *Bagrada stolidi* (HERRICH-SCHAEFFER, 1839)
Bagrada confusa HORVÁTH, 1936
Bagrada stolata HORVÁTH, 1936
Bagrada (Nitilia) stolata var. *quadrimaculata* HORVÁTH, 1936
Eurydema LAPORTE, 1833
- Note: RIDER (2006) notes that the taxonomy of *Eurydema* LAPORTE is complicated by the numerous varietal names (also called forms or aberrations) which are mostly nothing more than colour forms and should not be given subspecies status.
126. **Eurydema blanda* HORVÁTH, 1903
Described as new to Greece from Crete (HECKMANN *et al.* 2015). A species known otherwise only from Turkey.
127. **Eurydema eckerleini* JOSIFOV, 1961
Omitted from DROSOPOULOS (1980). First recorded in Crete (JOSIFOV 1961) and the Peloponnese (DERJANSCHI & PÉRICART 2005) and has now been recorded from Turkey, and recently from the Cyclades (SIMOGLOU & DIOLI 2017). No longer solely a Greek endemic species.
128. *Eurydema fieberi* FIEBER, 1837
DROSOPOULOS (1980) erroneously cites the authority as *E. fieberi* (SCHUMMEL).
129. *Eurydema oleracea* (LINNAEUS, 1758)
130. *Eurydema ornata* (LINNAEUS, 1758)
Cimex festivus LINNAEUS, 1767
Pentatoma pictum HERRICH-SCHAEFFER, 1833
Pentatoma decoratum HERRICH-SCHAEFFER, 1833
Eurydema ornata f. *decorata* (HERRICH-SCHAEFFER, 1834)
Eurydema festivum var. *chlorotica* HORVÁTH, 1891
(=*E. ornatum chlorotica* (HORVATH) OF DROSOPOULOS, 1980)
Eurydema festiva var. *pictella* KIRKALDY, 1909
131. **Eurydema rotundicollis* (DOHRN, 1860)
GÜNTHER (1990) records *E. rotundicollis* (DOHRN) new to Greece from the Vourinos mountains, NW Greece, cited by DERJANSCHI & PÉRICART (2005). Listed for Greece by RIDER (2006) without precise locality.
132. *Eurydema rugulosa* (DOHRN, 1860)
133. *Eurydema spectabilis* HORVÁTH, 1882
Recorded from the Peloponnese and Crete (DERJANSCHI & PÉRICART 2005). An additional record of this species for Greece is new to Lesvos; 1♂, Chroussos beach (on crucifer), Lesvos, 03.VI.2008, (39° 6'25.80"N 25°57'54.01"E), coll. & det. A.J. Ramsay.
134. *Eurydema ventralis* KOLENATI, 1846
Eurydema ornatum var. *ventralis* KOLENATI, 1846
Strachia ornata var. *pectoralis* FIEBER, 1861
Strachia ornata var. *dissimilis* FIEBER, 1861
- Note: numerous varieties were described from Italy by TAMANINI (1957).
- Stenozygum* FIEBER, 1861
135. *Stenozygum coloratum* (KLUG, 1845)
Stenozygum variegatum FIEBER, 1861

DERJANSCHI & PÉRICART (2005) cite a record of VIDAL (1949) without specific locality, and it is listed for Greece by RIDER (2006). A scarce species in Greece, with a recent record from Ialysos, Rhodes, 27 IX 2018, Tom Kruize, det. Leonidas-Romanos Davranoglou.

Trochiscocoris REUTER, 1890

136. **Trochiscocoris rotundatus rotundatus* HORVÁTH, 1895

GÜNTHER (1990) cites records from Agia Triada and the Vourinos mountains in NW Greece. DERJANSCHI & PÉRICART (2005) cite additional records from Mount Parnassos, central Greece and from the Peloponnese. Listed from Greece in RIDER (2006) with no specific locality.

Subfamily: Podopinae AMYOT & SERVILLE, 1843

Tribe Graphosomatini MULSANT & REY, 1865

Ancyrosoma AMYOT & SERVILLE, 1843

137. *Ancyrosoma leucogrammes* (GMELIN, 1790)

Cimex albolineatus FABRICIUS, 1781

Derula MULSANT & REY, 1856

138. *Derula flavoguttata* MULSANT & REY, 1856

Graphosoma LAPORTE, 1833

139. *Graphosoma italicum italicum* (O.F. MÜLLER, 1766)

Cimex italicus O.F. MÜLLER, 1766

Graphosoma lineatum italicum (O.F. MÜLLER, 1766)

Note: DROSOPULOS (1980) considered both *G. lineatum italicum* (O.F. MÜLLER, 1766) and *G. lineatum lineatum* (LINNAEUS, 1758) to be present in Greece, however RIDER (2006) listed only *G. lineatum* (LINNAEUS, 1758) as present in Greece, with *Cimex italicus* O.F. MÜLLER, 1766 as a junior synonym. Both *G. lineatum lineatum* (LINNAEUS, 1758) and *G. lineatum italicum* (O.F. MÜLLER, 1766) are regarded as subspecies by PÉRICART (2010) and both were cited from Greece. LUPOLI (2017) recently upgraded *G. lineatum italicum* (O.F. MÜLLER, 1766) to a full species in its own right, and distinct from *G. lineatum lineatum* (LINNAEUS, 1758), and regarded only *G. italicum* (O.F. MÜLLER, 1766) to be present in Greece. LUPOLI (2017) also cited specimens from eastern Crete which vary genetically but not morphologically from *G. italicum* (O.F. MÜLLER, 1766), but with no further clarification.

140. *Graphosoma semipunctatum* (FABRICIUS, 1775)

Graphosoma semipunctatum var. *subaequale* HORVÁTH, 1909

Graphosoma semipunctatum var. *anceps* HORVÁTH, 1909

Graphosoma creticum HORVÁTH, 1909

Graphosoma creticum var. *hemistictum* HORVÁTH, 1909

Note: *G. creticum* HORVÁTH was first described from Crete and subsequently recorded from Turkey (RIDER 2006). GAPON (2007) synonymised *G. creticum* HORVÁTH with *G. semipunctatum* (FABRICIUS) as it fell within the size range of that species. It is listed as a synonym of *G. semipunctatum* (FABRICIUS) in PÉRICART (2010) and AUKEMA *et al.* (2013). Genetic analysis has not been undertaken on *G. creticum* HORVÁTH.

Leprosoma BAERENSPRUNG, 1859

141. *Leprosoma inconspicuum* BAERENSPRUNG, 1859

Tholagmus STÄL, 1860

142. *Tholagmus flavolineatus* (FABRICIUS, 1798)

***Ventocoris* HAHN, 1834**

143. ***Ventocoris achivus*** (HORVÁTH, 1889)

Trigonosoma (Selenodera) falcatum var. *achivum* HORVÁTH, 1889

DROSOPoulos (1980) cites records of *V. falcatus falcatus* (CYRILLUS, 1791) and *Trigonosoma (Selenodera) falcatum* var. *reflexum* HORVÁTH, 1889 (cited as *V. falcatus reflexus*), and now a synonym of *V. falcatus* (CYRILLUS, 1791). RIDER (2006) notes that records of *V. falcatus* (CYRILLUS) from Greece are referable to *V. achivus* (HORVÁTH). Widespread in Greece (RIDER, 2006).

144. ***Ventocoris rusticus*** (FABRICIUS, 1781)

Ventocoris trigonus (KRYNICKI, 1871)

Note: *Ventocoris trigonus* (KRYNICKI, 1871) was listed for Greece by RIDER (2006) with records cited from the Cyclades by PÉRICART (2010). DURSUN & FENT (2013) subsequently synonymised *V. trigonus* (KRYNICKI) with *V. rusticus* (FABRICIUS), and included records of *V. rusticus* (FABRICIUS) from Athens and Crete. DURSUN & FENT (2013) concluded that despite regional differences in form in *V. rusticus* (FABRICIUS), the ostiole and peritreme shape remained constant in all Palearctic specimens examined.

Vilpianus STÄL, 1860

145. ****Vilpianus galii*** (WOLFF, 1802)

Not listed in RIDER (2006); PÉRICART (2010) cites records from the Peloponnese. AUKEMA *et al.* (2013) cite PÉRICART'S (2010) record for Greece.

Tribe Podopini AMYOT & SERVILLE, 1843

Podops LAPORTE, 1833

146. ***Podops curvidens*** A. COSTA, 1843

147. ***Podops rectidens*** HORVÁTH, 1883

Tribe Taxisini STÄL, 1872

Taxisa AMYOT & SERVILLE, 1843

148. ***Taxisa flavescens*** AMYOT & SERVILLE, 1843

Discussion

Very few studies have focussed on the fauna of the whole of Greece; JOSIFOV (1986a) and JOSIFOV & SIMOV (2006) considered the Greek fauna as part of a wider Balkans study including commentary on endemic species (JOSIFOV & SIMOV 2006), whilst WAGNER (1956), GÜNTHER (1990) and RIEGER (2007, 2012) provided data on a range of sites across Greece, including records of a number of species poorly known in Greece. Many of the studies on the Greek fauna in the 20th century have focussed on islands including Corfu (PAGANETTI-HUMMLER 1907); Thasos (JOSIFOV 1959); Crete (HEISS 1983, 1984, 1985, 1988, HEISS & GÜNTHER 1986, HEISS & HOPP 1987, HEISS *et al.* 1991, 1993, JOSIFOV & HEISS 1989, HECKMANN *et al.* 2015) and Santorini (RIEGER 1995).

Additional species recorded since DROSOPoulos (1980) are newly described species such as *Acrosternum malickyi* JOSIFOV & HEISS, *Byrsinus balcanicus* (JOSIFOV), *Ochetostethus heissi* MAGNIEN, *Odontotarsus crassus* KIRITSCHENKO; new discoveries, particularly from montane regions of northern and central Greece, including *Chlorochroa pinicola* (MULSANT & REY), *Eysarcoris venustissimus* (SCHRANK), *Tritomegas bicolor* (L.) and recent colonisation or introduction (*Andrallus spinidens* (FABRICIUS), *Halyomorpha halys* (STÄL), *Perillus*

bioculatus (FABRICIUS)). A significant proportion of recently recorded species in Greece are best regarded as Euro-Siberian species, perhaps due to historical collecting bias towards to the more southern parts of Greece and the islands rather than montane regions where many Euro-Siberian species occur within Greece.

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